

The HuT

Consortium meetings n.2

Deliverable D7.7

DEVELOPED WITHIN

WP7 Coordination and Management, T7.5 Consortium meetings

AUTHORS

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Version 1.0

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1. Technical references

Project Acronym	The HuT
Project Title	The Human-Tech Nexus - Building a Safe Haven to cope with Climate Extremes
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Deliverable No.	D7.7
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP7 - Coordination and Management
Task	T7.5 - Consortium meetings
Lead beneficiary	UNISA
Contributing beneficiary/ies	

- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

1.1. Document history

Version	Date	Lead contributor	Description
0.1	13.12.2023	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	First draft
0.2	22.12.2023	Guido Rianna (CMCC)	Critical review and proofreading
1.0	28.12.2023	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	Final version

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none

3. Annual meeting in Valencia (Spain)

3.1. Location and participants

The HuT end-of-year-one consortium meeting has been held on October 25-27, 2023, at Ciudad Politécnica de la Innovación of the Universitat Politècnica de València (Spain).

Table 1: Participant list

ID	Acronym	Name	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
1	UNISA	Michele Calvello	yes	yes	yes
1	UNISA	Alfonso Rossi Filangieri	yes	yes	yes
1	UNISA	Gaetano Pecoraro	yes	yes	yes
1	UNISA	Maria Vittoria Gargiulo	yes	yes	yes
2	CMCC	Guido Rianna	yes	yes	yes
2	CMCC	Costantino Battista Sirca	yes	yes	yes
2,1	CNR	Valentina Bacciu	yes	yes	yes
3	HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann	yes	yes	yes
3	HEREON	Anke Schluensen-Rico	yes	yes	yes
3	HEREON	Cicilia Lukman	yes	yes	yes
4	GFZ	Laurens Oostwegel	yes	yes	yes
5	IIASA	Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer	yes	yes	yes
5	IIASA	Florian Kraxner	yes	yes	
5	IIASA	Andrey Krasovski	yes	yes	
6	UPC	Marcel Hurlimann	yes	yes	yes
6	UPC	Flavio Asurza	yes	yes	yes
6	UPC	Nieves Lantada	yes	yes	
7	UPV	Javier Orozco-messana	yes	yes	
7	UPV	Adria Rubio-Martin	yes	yes	yes
7	UPV	Manuel Pulido-Velazquez	yes	yes	yes
7	UPV	Ana Gabriela Fernandez Garca	yes	yes	yes

7	UPV	Dariana Isamel Avila Velasquez	yes		
7	UPV	Eric Gielen	yes	yes	yes
7	UPV	Chele Esteve Sendra	yes	yes	yes
8	NGI	Laura Rødvand	yes	yes	yes
9	GWP-CEE	Anna Smetanova	yes	yes	yes
9	GWP-CEE	Primož Skrt	yes	yes	yes
10	HY	Sirkku Juhola	yes	yes	yes
10	HY	Janina Käyhkö	yes	yes	yes
11	IMO	Harpa Grímsdóttir	yes	yes	yes
11	IMO	Jón Kristinn Helgason	yes	yes	yes
11	IMO	Unnur Blær A. Bartsch	yes	yes	yes
12	VU	Gintautas Stankunavicius	yes	yes	yes
12	VU	Giedre Godiene	yes	yes	yes
13	ARANTEC	Eisharc Jaquet	yes	yes	yes
13	ARANTEC	Enrique Vidal	yes	yes	yes
13	ARANTEC	Francis Nieto Torres	yes	yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Péter Gergő Katona Mr.	yes	yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Péter Sólyom	yes	yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Gábor Harsányi	yes	yes	
15	ICONS	Ilaria Bonetti	yes	yes	yes
15	ICONS	Chiara Serio	yes	yes	yes
16	LEITHA	Antonio Tirri	yes	yes	yes
16	LEITHA	Francesco Lo Conti	yes	yes	yes
17	SOR	Silvana Gargiulo	yes	yes	yes
18	CONF-NO	Francesca Cossu	yes	yes	yes
19	NIP	Ingibjorg Lilja Omarsdottir	yes	yes	yes
20	MA	Tinna Kristbjorg Halldorsdottir	yes	yes	yes
20	MA	Hjordis Gudmundsdottir	yes	yes	yes
20	MA	Erna Rakel Baldvinsdóttir	yes	yes	yes

21	UNIGE	Anna Scolobig	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Mario Bruno Rohrer	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Jogscha Abderhalden	yes	yes	yes
22	UCL	Carina Fearnley	yes	yes	yes
22	UCL	Ilan Kelman	yes	yes	yes
22	UCL	Maryam Rokhideh	yes	yes	yes
23	MET	Joanne Robbins	yes	yes	yes
24	BGS	Katy Freeborough	yes	yes	yes
25	GNDR	Marcos Concepcion Raba	yes	yes	yes
*	LAP (and MET)	Brian Golding	yes	yes	yes
*	LAP	Manfred Staehli	(online)	(online)	(online)
*	LAP	Marleen de Ruiten	(online)	(online)	(online)
*	LAP	Irene Amuron			(online)
*	LAP	Gavin White	(online)		(online)
*	LEAP	Jonathan Pratschke			(online)
*	LEAP	Cees van Westen			(online)

Note: Besides the LAP and LEAP members explicitly listed in the table above, also other people from consortium partners attended online some parts of the meeting.

3.2. Agenda

Tuesday 24 October

- 16:00-18:30, **SCT meeting**
- 20:00 *Informal dinner and get-together*

Wednesday 25 October

- 09:00-09:30, **Welcome & Intro to The HuT annual meeting**
- 09:30-11:00, **Demonstrators' Arena (WP1)**
- COFFEE BREAK
- 11:30-13:00, **Human behaviors (WP2)**
- LUNCH BREAK
- 14:30-16:00, **Governance and Policy (WP3)**
- 16:00-17:00, **Science and Technology (WP4)**
- 17:00-17:30, **Art activity explanation**
- *Transfer to the Valencia Botanical Garden*
- 18:00-19:00 **Sci-Art activity at the Botanical**
- *Touristic tour around city center*

Thursday 26 October

- 09:00-10:30, **International DRR Nexus Forum (part 1)**
- COFFEE BREAK
- 11:00-13:00, **International DRR Nexus Forum (part 2)**
- LUNCH BREAK
- 14:30-15:30, **Demonstrators' pitches**
- 15:30-17:00, **Transferability and scalability (WP5)**
- *Side meetings & Free time*
- 20:30 **Consortium dinner**

Friday 27 October

- 09:00-10:30, **Linking WPs and DEMs: the way forward**
- 10:30-11:00, **General Assembly (WP7)**
- COFFEE BREAK
- 11:30-12:30, **CDE strategy (WP6)**
- 12:30-13:30, **Advisory Boards (LAP and LEAP) and EU networking**

3.3. Activities

All the activities listed in the Agenda have been carried out. The presentations and the video recordings of the sessions are shared internally using the google drive platform (see Deliverable 7.2 – Data management plan, <https://zenodo.org/records/10029991>)

3.3.1. Work Packages (WPs)

All the activities that are being conducted in the seven WPs were presented in the meeting.

Work package WP1 – Demonstrators’ arena. It was presented and discussed in the first day of the meeting. The session was structured as follows.

1. Summary of WP1 progress for the first 12 months
2. Interactive session: group activity to support to identify own roadmap for each DEM for local DRR nexus forum and The Hut for me and you narratives
 - Start with DEM5 roadmap as an example as presentation to describe the stakeholder engagement, DRR and CCA options and local DRR nexus forum
 - Break-out group exercise
 - Reporting of group discussion outcomes
3. Next steps for relevant deliverables (from WP1 and all WPs)
4. Cross-WP Discussion: mutual support of Demos and WPs to achieve synergies and goals of the project

Work package WP2 – Human behaviours. It was presented and discussed in the first day of the meeting. The session was structured as follows.

1. Summary of WP2 progress over the first 12 months
2. Interactive Activity
3. Designed activity to support and obtain feedback on WP2 plans
4. Warnings Database
5. Wrap Up

Work package WP3 – Governance and policy. It was presented and discussed in the first day of the meeting. The session was structured as follows.

1. Task 3.1: Enablers and barriers to multi-hazard/systemic risk reduction
2. Task 3.2: Robust decision support tools for multi/systemic risk policy making
3. Task 3.3: Insurance and risk financing instruments for DRR and local resilience

Work package WP4 – Science and Technology. It was presented and discussed in the first day of the meeting. The session was structured as follows.

1. Recap about the performed activities and lessons learnt
2. Deliverable 4.1 “SoA on prevention and preparedness DRR actions”
3. Deliverables 4.2 “Monitoring activities to be developed in the Demonstrators” and 4.5 “Modelling activities to be developed in the Demonstrators”
4. Working groups for key activities

5. Insights from the activities carried out in the first year: Monitoring in DEM3 and Dynamic Exposure Mapping
6. Final discussion

Work package WP5 – Transferability and scalability. It was presented and discussed in the second day of the meeting. The session was structured as follows.

1. First year working together
2. Amplifying framework
3. HuT amplifying stories mosaic
4. Reporting the amplifying process
5. Testing the prototype of reporting
6. Feedback collection
7. Next years steps

Work package WP6 – Communication, dissemination and exploitation. It was presented and discussed in the third day of the meeting. The session was structured as follows.

1. Activities done
2. Some data
3. Some tips for communication
4. Work to do
5. Let's hear from you

Work package WP7 – Coordination and Management. Coordination and management issues were addressed throughout the meeting, whenever needed, yet the main sessions devoted to these issues were the following.

- Intro to The HuT annual meeting (first day)
- Linking WPs and DEMs: the way forward (third day)
- General Assembly (third day)

3.3.2. Demonstrators (DEMs)

A session in the second day of the meeting was specifically devoted to the 10 Demonstrators, who were briefly presented as follows.

DEM 1 – Valencia (Spain). Investigated climate extremes: droughts, heatwaves. Main issues tackled: monitoring, modelling, urban pavements, forecasting.

DEM 2 – Val d'Aran Region (Spain). Investigated climate extremes: droughts, floods, forest fires, landslides. Main issues tackled: impact-based early warning, monitoring, modelling, data portal.

DEM 3 – Lattari mountains (Italy). Investigated climate extremes: floods, forest fires, landslides, storms. Main issues tackled: involvement of stakeholders, IoT monitoring, human sentinels, data portal.

DEM 4 – Vilnius (Lithuania). Investigated climate extremes: floods. Main issues tackled: historical flooding events, analysis of precipitation, rainwater treatment facilities, meeting with stakeholders.

DEM 5 – Schleswig-Holstein State (Germany). Investigated climate extremes: heatwaves, storms. Main issues tackled: stakeholders’ involvement, sci-art activities, serious gaming.

DEM 6 – East fjords (Iceland). Investigated climate extremes: floods, landslides. Main issues tackled: dissemination of data, information to inhabitants.

DEM 7 – Tisza River Basin (Hungary). Investigated climate extremes: floods. Main issues tackled: smart phone app for stakeholders, meeting with stakeholders.

DEM 8 – Ogliastra (Italy). Investigated climate extremes: droughts, forest fires, heatwaves. Main issues tackled: decision support system, stakeholder engagement, insurance products.

DEM 9 – Dorset (UK). Investigated climate extremes: floods, landslides, storms. Main issues tackled: stakeholder meeting, IoT monitoring, forecasting of severe convection.

DEM 10 – Berne Canton (Switzerland). Investigated climate extremes: floods, landslides, storms. Main issues tackled: monitoring, data sharing, stakeholder needs.

3.3.3. International DRR Nexus Forum (I-DRRnF) workshop

The morning of the second day of the meeting was devoted to first edition of the International DRR Nexus Forum workshop, entitled “Co-creating inclusive disaster risk reduction strategies”. More details on the workshop are available in deliverable D.5.3 - “Minutes from the I-DRRnF workshops”.

3.3.4. General Assembly

The second General Assembly of The HuT was held on Friday 27 October 2023, during the third day of the meeting. Table 2 shows the list of participants.

Table 2: Participants in General Assembly

Partner	Name
UNISA	Michele Calvello
CMCC	Guido Rianna
CNR	Valentina Bacciu
HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann
GFZ	Laurens JN Oostwegel
IIASA	Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer
UPC	Marcel Hurlimann
UPV	Manuel Pulido-Velazquez
NGI	Laura Rødvand
GWP-CEE	Anna Smetanova
HY	Sirkku Juhola

IMO	Harpa Grímsdóttir
VU	Gintautas Stankunavicius
ARANTEC	Eisharc Jaquet
KOTIVIZIG	Gábor Harsányi
ICONS	Ilaria Bonetti
LEITHA	Francesco Lo Conti
SOR	Silvana Gargiulo
CONF-NO	Francesca Cossu
NIP	Ingibjorg Lilja Omarsdottir
MA	Erna Rakel Baldvinsdóttir
UNIGE	Anna Scolobig
UCL	Carina Fearnley
MET	Joanne Robbins
BGS	Katy Freeborough
GNDR	Marcos Concepcion Raba

The General Assembly has given mandate to coordinator and project manager to present a request to amend the Grant Agreement, addressing the deliverables. The updated list of deliverables is reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Main features of The HuT deliverables (in black the ones already published, in red the deliverables that need editing)

	Type	Lead	Delivery month	Reviewer	Previous name (delivery month)
D1.1 – Ongoing activities in the demonstrators	Synopsis	HEREON	15	GWP-CEE	D1.1 (11, 23, 35, 47)
D1.7 – Ongoing activities in the demonstrators n.2	Synopsis	HEREON	28	GWP-CEE	New
D1.8 – Ongoing activities in the demonstrators n.3	Synopsis	HEREON	45	GWP-CEE	New
D1.2 – Composition of Local DRR nexus Forums	Report	HEREON	16	GNDR	D1.2 (12)
D1.3 – Architecture of demonstrator's data portal	Template	NGI	6	GFZ	D1.3 (6)

	Type	Lead	Delivery month	Reviewer	Previous name (delivery month)
D1.4 – ‘The Hut for Me and You’	Template	UNIGE	3	UCL	D1.4 (3)
D1.5 – ‘The Hut for Me and You’ narratives	Report	HEREON	16	UCL	D1.5 (12, 24, 36)
D1.9 – ‘The Hut for Me and You’ narratives n.2	Report	HEREON	38	UCL	New
D1.6 – Standard protocol for evaluating warning systems	Template	MET	15	NIP	D1.6 (14)
D2.1 – SoA on Human-centric DRR activities	Report	UCL	6	HY	D2.1 (6)
D2.2 – Communicating warning messages	Report	UCL	28	KOTIVIZIG	D2.2 (24)
D2.3 – How warnings can be better integrated within society	Policy briefs	UCL	42	GWP-CEE	D2.3 (42)
D2.4 – Co-developing DRR solutions with communities	Report	GNDR	36	UPC	D2.4 (36)
D2.5 – Educational material produced	Report	UPV	36	BGS	D2.5 (36, 48)
D3.1 – Innovative policy/governance enablers for multi-risk DRR	Report	UNIGE	32	GNDR	D3.1 (32)
D3.2 – Climate-proofing planning	Guidelines	CMCC	36	IMO	D3.2 (36)
D3.3 – Enablers/barriers of wide-scale implementation of nature-based solutions	Policy brief	IIASA	42	BGS	D3.3 (42)
D3.4 – Quantitative and multi-criteria analyses for multi-risk DRR	Report	HEREON	24	UPV	D3.4 (24)
D3.5 – Serious games for cascading and compound impacts	Manual	GFZ	42	UPV	D3.5 (42)
D3.6 – Prototype of innovative insurance product validated by user groups	Report	CMCC	27	UNISA	D3.6 (24)
D3.7 – Innovative risk transfer and financing for DRR	Report	CMCC	42	UNISA	D3.7 (42)
D4.1 – SoA on prevention and preparedness DRR actions	Report	CMCC	6	ARANTEC	D4.1 (6)

	Type	Lead	Delivery month	Reviewer	Previous name (delivery month)
D4.2 – Monitoring activities to be developed in the Demonstrators	Plan	ARANTEC	8	MET	D4.2 (8)
D4.3 – Ongoing monitoring activities in the Demonstrators	Synopsis	ARANTEC	30	VU	D4.3 (29)
D4.4 – The HuT innovative nexus monitoring activities – lessons learned	Report	ARANTEC	44	MET	D4.4 (44)
D4.5 – Modelling activities to be developed in the Demonstrators	Plan	UNISA	9	HEREON	D4.5 (9)
D4.6 – Ongoing modelling activities in the Demonstrators	Synopsis	UNISA	30	UNIGE	D4.6 (30)
D4.7 – The HuT innovative nexus modelling activities- lessons learned	Report	UNISA	44	HEREON	D4.7 (44)
D5.1 – Approaches to transfer DRR innovations	Report	GWP-CEE	15	VU	D5.1 (12)
D5.2 – Documenting DRR solutions and the transfer processes	Template	GWP-CEE	15	KOTIVIZIG	D5.2 (12)
D5.3 – Minutes from I-DRRnF workshops	Report	UNIGE	16	NGI	D5.3 (12, 24, 36)
D5.7 – Minutes from I-DRRnF workshops n.2	Report	UNIGE	28	NGI	New
D5.8 – Minutes from I-DRRnF workshops n.3	Report	UNIGE	40	NGI	New
D5.4 – Feedback of Field Visits	Report	GNDR	43	ICONS	D5.4 (25, 31, 37, 43)
D5.5 – Amplification Roadmap	Report	GWP-CEE	45	UNISA	D5.5 (45)
D5.6 – Scaling up DRR and CCA solutions	Policy Brief	HEREON	48	UNISA	D5.6 (48)
D6.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results	Plan	ICONS	6	IIASA	D6.1 (6, 36)
D6.5 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results n.2	Plan	ICONS	36	IIASA	New
D6.2 – Outreach and engagement activities	Synopsis	MET	22	LEITHA	D6.2 (18, 30, 42)

	Type	Lead	Delivery month	Reviewer	Previous name (delivery month)
D6.6 – Outreach and engagement activities n.2	Synopsis	MET	46	LEITHA	New
D6.3 – Networking activities	Synopsis	MET	22	UNIGE	D6.3 (24, 36, 48)
D6.7 – Networking activities n.2	Synopsis	MET	46	UNIGE	New
D6.4 – Consolidation of the Exploitation Plan	Plan	ICONS	48	IIASA	D6.4 (48)
D7.1 – Project management Plan	Plan	UNISA	3	CMCC	D7.1 (3)
D7.2 – Data management Plan	Plan	UNISA	6	ARANTEC	D7.2 (6, 24, 42)
D7.6 – Data management Plan n.2	Plan	UNISA	30	ARANTEC	New
D7.3 – Risk management Plan	Plan	UNISA	6	CMCC	D7.3 (6)
D7.4 – Ethical requirements Plan	Plan	UNISA	3	CMCC	D7.4 (3)
D7.5 – Consortium meetings	Report	UNISA	2	CMCC	D7.5 (2, 12, 24, 36, 48)
D7.7 – Consortium meetings n.2	Report	UNISA	15	CMCC	New
D7.8 – Consortium meetings n.3	Report	UNISA	27	CMCC	New
D7.9 – Consortium meetings n.4	Report	UNISA	39	CMCC	New

